

Blood and gore: The prevalence of violence in fanfiction across gender categories and engagement

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Introduction

Metadata, such as user-generated tags and popularity metrics, are controversial in (computational) fanfiction research. On the one hand, metadata are informative on both fanfiction content (Pianzola et al. 2020) and community (Brottrager et al. 2023), represent a user-generated, bottom-up source of information (Price 2019), and avoid the ethical and copyright-related problems associated with studying fanfiction texts (Neugarten et al. 2025a). On the other hand, the generalizability of tag analysis, which is the question of whether “tags retain their meaning and function across fandoms” (Nelson & Bullard 2025, 128) and tags’ contextual nature (Gursoy et al. 2018, 503), create interpretive difficulties.

This paper seeks to replicate some of the findings from Neugarten (2024) by studying whether intimate violence, and associated gender-based oppression, correlates with relationship types in fanfiction. We use the user-generated freeform tags and category tags available on fanfiction website *Archive of Our Own* (AO3)¹ to investigate the link between the prevalence of violence and gender. Specifically, we focus on the gender of fanfiction’s protagonists in romantic relationships (see Appendix 1). Additionally, we analyze whether the interaction of violence and gender has an effect on fan appreciation, operationalized as the ratio of kudos (i.e., likes) to hits (the K/H ratio).

This paper contributes to an analysis of fanfiction’s transformative potential. Fanfiction has sometimes been attributed the capacity to rewrite cultural norms, including those associated with the distribution of gendered power in stories (Neugarten 2025c). This is because fanfiction is written “outside of the literary marketplace” (Coppa 2017, 2) and is thus not as indebted to market forces as published fiction, and because fanfiction is predominantly written and read by people who fall outside of the culturally dominant category of cishet men (Rouse & Stanfill 2025). Our added focus on fan appreciation – operationalized here through the K/H ratio – is a way to place the interventions fanfiction may make in the power dynamics of its source materials, and more generally in the ideological structures of patriarchy, in the context of fan community norms as expressed through reader appreciation.

¹ <https://archiveofourown.org/>

Methods

Data

This study uses *MythFic Metadata* (Neugarten, 2024) – metadata about 5154 works of fanfiction in *Ancient Greek Religion and Lore* fandom – combined with a corpus of 9000 fanfiction stories based on *Harry Potter*, *Percy Jackson*, and *Lord of the Rings* (Jacobsen et al., 2024; Neugarten et al., 2025b).

We identified whether the freeform tags for each fanfic contained any of our specified violence tags (see Appendix 2). We only kept fics tagged with either F/M or M/M, as we are interested in gendered violence, and F/F unfortunately constituted too small a group for proper comparison (see Figure 1). Finally, we identified and removed outliers, defined as the fics with the top 0.05% highest K/H ratio (meaning a cut-off at a K/H ratio of 19).

Figure 1: Frequency of each category tag across fandoms

Analysis

After preprocessing, we had 9152 rows from 8302 unique fics and 5255 unique authors. The discrepancy between the number of rows and the number of unique fics is due to the fact that one fic can have multiple category tags and thus multiple rows in the dataframe. Table 1 presents descriptive statistics.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the corpus

Fandom	N. rows	N. authors	% violence	Avg. K/H ratio
AGRL	3260	1633	16.0	6.0
HP	2193	1641	14.5	5.0
LOTR	1431	788	15.6	5.8

<i>PJ</i>	2268	1224	12.8	5.8
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We created two mixed effects statistical models to test for the effects of category, violence, and appreciation within our corpus.

Model (1) is a mixed effects logistic regression that seeks to predict the relationship category based on an interaction between the prevalence of violence and the fic's K/H ratio with a main effect of fandom. We control for the effect of repeated authors by adding a random intercept for author.

$$(1) \text{ Category} \sim \text{violence} * \text{K/H ratio} + \text{fandom} + (1 | \text{author})$$

Model (2) is a linear mixed effects model that seeks to predict the K/H ratio for a fic based on an interaction between category and prevalence of violence as well as the fandom. Again, we add a random intercept for author.

$$(2) \text{ K/H ratio} \sim \text{category} * \text{violence} + \text{fandom} + (1 | \text{author})$$

Results

The output of model (1) is reported in Table 2. F/M and AGRL are the baseline category and fandom.

Table 2: Output for model (1)

Fixed effect	Estimate	Odds ²	Std. error	Z-value	P-value
<i>Violence</i>	0.32	1.37 (37%)	0.15	2.15	<0.05*
<i>K/H ratio</i>	0.15	1.16 (16%)	0.0098	14.85	<0.05*
<i>HP</i>	0.97	2.63 (163%)	0.082	11.83	<0.05*
<i>LOTR</i>	0.91	2.49 (149%)	0.095	9.59	<0.05*
<i>PJ</i>	0.90	2.46 (146%)	0.084	10.72	<0.05*
<i>Violence : K/H ratio</i>	0.004	1.0036 (0.36%)	0.026	0.14	0.89

As illustrated in Figure 2, we find that M/M-stories are significantly more likely to contain violence and have a higher K/H ratio than F/M-stories. We find no interaction effect, meaning the effect of the K/H ratio is similar regardless of the prevalence of violence. We also find that *HP*, *LOTR*, and *PJ* all have significantly more M/M fics than F/M compared to *AGRL*. This aligns with existing research, as 65.8% of AO3-users described themselves as primarily interested in M/M pairings (Rouse & Stanfill 2025).

Model (2) shows whether either category is more appreciated and how the prevalence of violence might influence appreciation across categories. The model output is presented in Table 3.

² The odds are calculated by computing the exponential function of the coefficient estimates from a logistic regression model. This indicates the average change in the odds of a fic being M/M when the predictor increases one step (i.e., goes from *AGRL* to *HP*, or an increase in the K/H ratio).

Figure 2: Regression lines between the K/H ratio and relationship categories for fics with and without violence across fandoms (left) and for the corpus combined (right).

Table 3: Output for model (2)

Fixed effect	Estimate	Std. Error	T-value	P-value
<i>M/M</i>	1.0	0.069	14.53	<0.05*
<i>Violence</i>	-0.94	0.12	-7.73	<0.05*
<i>HP</i>	-1.16	0.10	-11.08	<0.05*
<i>LOTR</i>	-0.32	0.13	-2.50	<0.05*
<i>PJ</i>	-0.58	0.11	-5.23	<0.05*
<i>M/M : violence</i>	-0.38	0.16	-2.40	<0.05*

As illustrated in Figure 3, we find that M/M fics in general have a significantly greater K/H ratio than F/M, and the prevalence of violence significantly decreases the K/H ratio for a given fic. The significant interaction effect means that this decrease in appreciation is greater for M/M fics containing violence than F/M fics.

Together, our models show that M/M fanfics, despite containing more violence in general, are less appreciated for doing so.

Figure 3: The mean and distribution of the K/H ratio for each relationship category in each violence group across fandoms. Error bars indicate the 95% confidence interval of the mean.

Discussion

Neugarten (2024) found the connection between violence and gender to partly depend on the type of violence, e.g., physical or sexual. Overall, however, they found F/M stories overrepresented in several violence categories. This contrasts with our findings, which show that M/M fics are more likely to contain violence. This was also the case for *AGRL*, which is surprising, as it is the only fandom with a larger proportion of F/M than M/M in the corpus. In other words, although there are fandom-specific levels of F/M and M/M, they exhibit a similar pattern when it comes to the prevalence of violence.

This focus on the overall presence of violence instead of categories of violence as in Neugarten (2024) does present one limitation. In future studies, we wish to investigate the prevalence of different types of violence across these fandoms. Additionally, we only focused on one type of engagement metric, the K/H ratio. As shown in Jacobsen and Kristensen-McLachlan (2025), although the K/H ratio seeks to neutralize the effect of popularity, it can create bias against certain types of fanfiction which are revisited more and thus have more hits relative to their likes. In future studies, we wish to investigate this further. Finally, as mentioned in the introduction, using only metadata is controversial within fanfiction research. Similarly, this analysis does not tell us anything about who is doing the violence against whom. An NLP approach that looks at the text itself and its relation to violence would be a fruitful direction for future research.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Explanation of relationship type tags available on AO3 and the associated gender of the story's protagonists.

Relationship Tag	Explanation
F/M	female/male - romantic and/or sexual
M/M	male/male - romantic and/or sexual
F/F	female/female - romantic and/or sexual
Gen	No romantic or sexual pairings, no information about protagonists' gender
Multi	Multiple romantic or sexual pairings, no information about protagonists' gender
Other	Does not fit other tags, no information about protagonists' gender

Appendix 2

Tags used as indicators of violence and violent content. They are divided into categories to fit the methodology of Neugarten (2024), however, for this study we looked at the presence of any of the tags.

We followed a similar procedure as Neugarten (2024), and manually identified violence-related tags in the top 500 tags for each fandom. Due to this manual procedure, the tags are subject to personal biases and interpretations of what constitutes "violence". This is especially pertinent for 'Roughness' which has been included before in the study of violence (Neugarten, 2024), but was in later studies disregarded (Neugarten, 2025c) as these tags are perhaps more aligned with consensual sexual acts than acts of violence indicative of gendered power imbalances. Nonetheless, even the occurrence of consensual violence indicates that texts are interrogating the topic of gendered power.

We decided to keep the 'Roughness' tag for future studies that can take a more granular look at the use of violence-related tags. Additionally, a control analysis showed that excluding the Roughness tags did not drastically change the results of this study (see Appendix 3).

Violence Category	Associated Tags
Physical	Abuse, blood, blood and gore, blood and injury, blood and violence, canon-typical violence, implied/referenced abuse, implied/referenced torture, injury, major character injury, minor violence, torture, violence, whump ³
Roughness	BDSM, biting, bondage, choking, light BDSM, light bondage, spanking
Sexual	Dubious consent, gang rape, implied/referenced rape/non-con, mildly dubious consent, rape, rape/non-con elements

³ From [Urban Dictionary](#): "Whump: A fandom term, [commonly](#) used by fan fiction authors ([particularly](#) in the Stargate genre) to describe physical and/or [mental abuse](#) laid on a character in a story."

Death	Canonical character death, character death, death, implied/referenced character death, minor character death, murder, temporary character death
Emotional	Bullying, emotional manipulation, emotional/psychological abuse, homophobia, manipulation, period-typical sexism
Kidnapping	Abduction, kidnapping

Appendix 3

Here we report the results of the control analysis. The control analysis consists of the same models, but excluding the ‘Roughness’ category of violence.

The output of model (1) with control data is reported below. F/M and AGRL are the baseline category and fandom.

It is worth noting that, although the estimate for the main effect of violence remains similar, the effect is no longer significant. As there is already a great imbalance in the two groups (violence / no violence), the signal of the effect of violence can be difficult for the model to estimate without the additional data that Roughness provides. The similar effect size indicates that including Roughness does not change the outcome much, but it does make the signal easier to pick up for the model.

Fixed effect	Estimate	Odds	Std. error	Z-value	P-value
<i>Violence</i>	0.22	1.24 (24%)	0.16	1.39	0.16
<i>K/H ratio</i>	0.14	1.15 (15%)	0.0097	14.76	<0.05*
<i>HP</i>	0.96	2.62 (162%)	0.082	11.79	<0.05*
<i>LOTR</i>	0.91	2.49 (149%)	0.095	9.59	<0.05*
<i>PJ</i>	0.89	2.46 (146%)	0.084	10.64	<0.05*
<i>Violence : K/H ratio</i>	0.005	1.0054 (0.54%)	0.027	0.20	0.84

Similarly, the output for model (2) with control data is reported below.

Fixed effect	Estimate	Std. Error	T-value	P-value
<i>M/M</i>	0.98	0.069	14.32	<0.05*
<i>Violence</i>	-0.65	0.13	-4.99	<0.05*
<i>HP</i>	-1.16	0.11	-11.02	<0.05*
<i>LOTR</i>	-0.32	0.13	-2.53	<0.05*
<i>PJ</i>	-0.55	0.11	-5.00	<0.05*
<i>M/M : violence</i>	-0.35	0.17	-2.08	<0.05*